

P versus NP

FRANK VEGA, Joysonic, Serbia

P versus NP is considered as one of the most important open problems in computer science. This consists in knowing the answer of the following question: Is P equal to NP? It is one of the seven Millennium Prize Problems selected by the Clay Mathematics Institute. This question was first mentioned in a letter written by John Nash to the National Security Agency in 1955. A precise statement of the P versus NP problem was introduced independently in 1971 by Stephen Cook and Leonid Levin. Since that date, all efforts to find a proof for this problem have failed. To attack the P versus NP question the concept of NP-completeness has been very useful. If any single NP-complete problem can be solved in polynomial time, then every NP problem has a polynomial time algorithm. Quadratic Congruences is a known NP-complete problem. We prove Quadratic Congruences is in P. In this way, we demonstrate the P versus NP problem.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Complexity Classes, NP-complete, Polynomial Time, Quadratic Congruence, Millennium Problem

1 RESULTS

An important complexity class is *NP-complete* [5]. A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is *NP-complete* if

- $L \in NP$, and
- $L' \leq_p L$ for every $L' \in NP$.

If L is a language such that $L' \leq_p L$ for some $L' \in NP$ -complete, then L is *NP-hard* [3]. Moreover, if $L \in NP$, then $L \in NP$ -complete [3].

Definition 1.1. Given four positive integers a, b, c and x , the following Boolean function $Q(a, b, c, x)$ is true if and only if $x^2 \equiv a \pmod{b}$ and $x < c$.

Definition 1.2. QUADRATIC CONGRUENCES

INSTANCE: Positive integers a, b and c , such that we have the prime factorization of b .

QUESTION: Is there a positive integer x such that $Q(a, b, c, x) = true$?

We denote this problem as *QC*. $QC \in NP$ -complete [5].

THEOREM 1.3. $QC \in P$.

PROOF. *QC* is solvable in polynomial time if $c = \infty$ when the prime factorization of b is given [5]. Since we can have a candidate solution $x \geq c$ in polynomial time [9], then we can find another positive integer i such that $i < x$ and $Q(a, b, c, i) = true$. Hence, we obtain $x^2 \equiv i^2 \pmod{b}$. Then $x^2 - i^2 \equiv (x - i) \times (x + i) \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$. Thus $(x - (c - j)) \times (x + (c - j)) \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$ where $1 \leq j \leq c - 1$ since $i < c$. However, if we have $(x - (c - j)) \times (x + (c - j)) \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$, then we obtain either $(x - (c - j)) \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$ or $(x + (c - j)) \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$ or both. This can be transformed into $(x - c + j) \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$ or $(x + c - j) \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$ and therefore, $(x - c) \equiv -j \pmod{b}$ or $(x + c) \equiv j \pmod{b}$. Nevertheless, we have the values of x and c , and so we can calculate $(x - c)$ and $(x + c)$. After this calculation, we only need to check whether there exists this integer $1 \leq j \leq c - 1$ which complies with $(x - c) = b \times k - j$ or $(x + c) = b \times k' + j$ for the possible values of integers $k \geq 0$ and $k' \geq 0$. Now, we need to find b' and b'' which are the nearest multiples of b which are greater than $(x - c)$ or lesser than $(x + c)$ respectively such that $b' - (x - c)$ or $(x + c) - b''$ are the possible minimum values of j greater than 0. Consequently, the calculation of j is trivial since it will be equal to $b' - (x - c) = j$ or $(x + c) - b'' = j$. We must guarantee in the calculation of b' and b'' that

$b' \neq (x - c)$ and $b'' \neq (x + c)$. Since the calculation of b' and b'' can be done in polynomial time from the values $(x - c)$ and $(x + c)$, then $QC \in P$. Certainly, b' can be calculated as

$$b' = b \times (\lceil \frac{(x - c)}{b} \rceil + \lfloor \frac{(x + c)}{b} \rfloor)$$

and b'' can be calculated as

$$b'' = b \times (\lfloor \frac{(x + c)}{b} \rfloor - \lceil \frac{(x - c)}{b} \rceil)$$

where $\lceil s \rceil$ and $\lfloor s \rfloor$ are the ceiling and the floor functions of a real number s and $\lceil s \rceil$ is equal to 1 when s is an integer otherwise $\lceil s \rceil$ is equal to 0. In case of we cannot find this integer j such that $1 \leq j \leq c - 1$, then it will not exist $i < x$ when $Q(a, b, c, i) = true$. On the other hand, in case of this integer $1 \leq j \leq c - 1$ is found, then it will exist $c - j = i < x$ such that $Q(a, b, c, i) = true$. \square

THEOREM 1.4. $P = NP$.

PROOF. If any single NP -complete problem can be solved in polynomial time, then $P = NP$ [8]. As a consequence of Theorem 1.3, the answer of the P versus NP problem will be $P = NP$. Cryptography, for example, relies on certain problems being difficult. A constructive and efficient solution to an NP -complete problem such as 3SAT will break most existing cryptosystems including: Public-key cryptography [6], symmetric ciphers [7] and one-way functions used in cryptographic hashing [4]. These would need to be modified or replaced by information-theoretically secure solutions not inherently based on P - NP equivalence. There are enormous consequences that will follow from rendering tractable many currently mathematically intractable problems. For instance, many problems in operations research are NP -complete, such as some types of integer programming and the traveling salesman problem [5]. Efficient solutions to these problems have enormous implications for logistics [1]. Many other important problems, such as some problems in protein structure prediction, are also NP -complete, so this will spur considerable advances in biology [2]. Indeed, a proof of $P = NP$ could solve not merely one Millennium Problem but all seven of them [1]. This observation is based on once we fix a formal system such as the first-order logic plus the axioms of ZF set theory, then we can find a demonstration in time polynomial in n when a given statement has a proof with at most n symbols long in that system [1]. This is assuming that the other six Clay conjectures have ZF proofs that are not too large. \square

REFERENCES

- [1] Scott Aaronson. 2017. $P \stackrel{?}{=} NP$. *Electronic Colloquium on Computational Complexity, Report No. 4* (2017).
- [2] Bonnie Berger and Tom Leighton. 1998. Protein folding in the hydrophobic-hydrophilic (HP) model is NP-complete. *Journal of Computational Biology* 5, 1 (1998), 27–40. <https://doi.org/10.1145/279069.279080>
- [3] Thomas H. Cormen, Charles E. Leiserson, Ronald L. Rivest, and Clifford Stein. 2009. *Introduction to Algorithms* (3 ed.). The MIT Press.
- [4] Debapratim De, Abishek Kumarasubramanian, and Ramarathnam Venkatesan. 2007. Inversion Attacks on Secure Hash Functions Using sat Solvers. In *International Conference on Theory and Applications of Satisfiability Testing*. Springer, 377–382. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-72788-0_36
- [5] Michael R. Garey and David S. Johnson. 1979. *Computers and Intractability: A Guide to the Theory of NP-Completeness* (1 ed.). San Francisco: W. H. Freeman and Company.
- [6] Satoshi Horie and Osamu Watanabe. 1997. Hard instance generation for SAT. *Algorithms and Computation* (1997), 22–31. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-63890-3_4
- [7] Fabio Massacci and Laura Marraro. 2000. Logical Cryptanalysis as a SAT Problem. *Journal of Automated Reasoning* 24, 1 (2000), 165–203. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006326723002>
- [8] Christos H. Papadimitriou. 1994. *Computational complexity*. Addison-Wesley.
- [9] René Schoof. 1985. Elliptic curves over finite fields and the computation of square roots mod p . *Mathematics of computation* 44, 170 (1985), 483–494.